

Extraction and fractionation of lipid components of soil by chromatographic methods

Lyu-Lyan-Min E.I., Shamrikova E.V., Gruzdev I.V., Zhangurov E.V.

Institute of Biology Komi SC UrD RAS, Syktyvkar, Russian Federation, gruzdeva.e@ib.komisc.ru

Keywords: aliphatic acids, aliphatic alcohols, alkanes, gas chromatography/mass spectrometry
doi: 10.5281/zenodo.17323311

The maintenance of soil structure, as well as the preservation of its biodiversity, depends on the contribution of various fractions of soil organic matter, where the most important is the lipid fraction, which is directly related to the soil microbiome [1]. The lipid components (LC) of the soil include numerous organic compounds, ranging from complex molecules (phospholipids, peptidolipids, glycolipids, etc.) to simpler ones such as alkanes, ketones, alcohols, and carboxylic acids, which often act as indicators of chemical and biochemical processes occurring in the soil [2].

The accelerated solvent extraction (ASE) method was used to extract LC of the soil, allowing the use of organic extractants at elevated temperature and pressure. Heating (up to 150 °C) accelerates the extraction process, while high pressure (up to 12 MPa) allows the extractant to be kept in a liquid state over a wide temperature range. We have shown that only the extractant temperature has a significant effect on the extraction of organic compounds of different classes from the soil using the ASE method. Chromatographic methods are traditionally used to analyze soil extracts for the content of LC. However, the use of even highly efficient capillary columns is often accompanied by the imposition of chromatographic peaks of the components, which leads to unreliable information about the qualitative and quantitative composition. An increase in the selectivity of the determination of LC of the soil can be achieved by their preliminary fractionation. The method of column adsorption chromatography was used to fractionate the isolated LC. The two most common sorbents were considered: silica gel and aluminum oxide.

Unlike the known approaches, the extract was mixed with a sorbent and evaporated directly on the sorbent, which avoids over-dissolution of the residue and preserves the volatile components of the extract. After the transfer of the sorbent (Al₂O₃) to the column, the alkane hydrocarbon fraction was isolated with hexane.

Repeated elution of the sorbed components with diethyl ether allows us to isolate the fraction of higher aliphatic alcohols.

The fraction of fatty acids was isolated directly from the sorbent by direct methanolysis, which eliminates the stage of elution of acids and ensures their quantitative determination.

The developed approach was applied to the analysis of LC of soils of the Polar Urals on carbonate rocks (Bolshoy Paipudynsky Ridge).

The research was carried out within the framework of the RNF grant № 24-27-00231 «Carbonate soil-permafrost geosystems of the Polar Urals: polygenesis, evolution, classification»

References

1. Willers C., Jansen van Rensburg P.J., Claassens S. Phospholipid fatty acid profiling of microbial communities—a review of interpretations and recent applications // *J. Appl. Microbiol.* 2015. V. 119. № 5. P. 1207–1218. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jam.12902>
2. Otto A., Shunthirasingham C., Simpson M. J.A comparison of plant and microbial biomarkers in grassland soils from the Prairie Ecozone of Canada // *Org. Geochem.* 2005. V. 36. № 13. P. 425–448. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.orggeochem.2004.09.008>.